

CODEN [USA]: IAJPBB

ISSN: 2349-7750

**INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>

Research Article

**ADHERENCE TO SAUDI NEPHROPATHY SCREENING
PROGRAM IN PRIMARY HEALTH CARE CENTER IN
ALKHOBAR CITY**¹Dr. Esam Yahya Qugandi, ² Dr. Adel Aldossari¹Ministry of Health, KSA, R3 Family Medicine Resident, Security Forces Hospital Program, Dammam, KSA; ²Family and Community Medicine Consultant, Security Forces Hospital, Dammam, KSA**Article Received:** June 2019**Accepted:** July 2019**Published:** August 2019**Abstract:**

Background: Chronic kidney disease (CKD) affects approximately 13% of the adult population, resulting in significant morbidity, mortality and health care costs.

Method: A Cross-sectional study was conducted among Patients with type II diabetes or hypertension or both in chronic disease clinics (CDC) in PHC centers in Eastern Province to assess adherence to nephropathy screening guideline among physicians in chronic disease clinics.

Results: The study included 246 patients, the majority 51.6% was females. 40.2% of patients had type 2 diabetes mellitus, 24.4% had hypertension and 35.4% had both. There were only 26% of cases follow guideline in screening of nephropathy.

Conclusion: The study concluded that the majority of cases do not follow nephropathy screening guideline. We recommend decision makers to conduct further planning on increasing the adherence level and the outcomes of the screening program.

Corresponding author:**Dr. Esam Yahya Qugandi,**Ministry of Health, KSA, R3 Family Medicine Resident,
Security Forces Hospital Program, Dammam, KSA.

QR code

Please cite this article in press Esam Yahya Qugandi et al., *Adherence To Saudi Nephropathy Screening Program In Primary Health Care Center In Alkhobar City., Indo Am. J. P. Sci, 2019; 06[08].*

BACKGROUND:

Chronic kidney disease (CKD) is a major health problem in Saudi Arabia. There has been a noticeable rise in the prevalence and incidence of end stage chronic kidney disease (CKD) in Saudi Arabia over the last three decades. This rise exceeds those reported from many countries. Diabetic nephropathy and hypertensive nephropathy are the two major causes of CKD (43%, and 36% respectively). Deaths from ESRD were 2.21% annually. Of those 12% dying with CKD in Saudi Arabia annually, we estimated that two thirds were diabetics.¹

The prevalence of diabetic nephropathy among dialysis patients in Saudi Arabia has increased by 162% in the last twenty-five years.¹ Hypertension, on the other hand, affects more than 25% of the adult Saudi population.² Perform an annual test to assess urine albumin excretion in all type 2 diabetic patients starting at diagnosis. Measure serum creatinine at least annually in all adults with diabetes regardless of the degree of urine albumin excretion.³

According to NICE guidelines, CKD is classified into 5 grades based on glomerular filtration rate (GFR) and Albumin Creatinine Ratio (ACR) : (Normal : 90<=, Mild : 89-60, Moderate: 59-30, Severe : 29-15 and :Kidney Failure: 15>=).⁴

Kidney disease often has no symptoms in its early stage, therefore, adherence to nephropathy screening program plays a vital role in early detection, intervention, and treatment.

Frequency of requesting renal profile based on Saudi National Nephropathy screening guidelines (as recommendation from American Diabetics Association ADA2017)^{5,6}, is to be run annually for all patients, every 6 months if eGFR 45-60 ml/min/1.73m², every 3 months if eGFR 30-44 ml/min/1.73m².

LITERATURE REVIEW:

Microalbuminuria is considered the earliest sign of Diabetic nephropathy. In Saudi National diabetic registry study which was done in 54,670 type 2 diabetic patients, 10.8% of them have diabetic nephropathy divided into 1.2% Microalbuminuria, 8.1 Macroalbuminurea and 1.5% End Stage Renal Disease.⁷

By the end of 2008, there were 10,203 patients on hemodialysis, 966 on peritoneal dialysis, and 7836 with functioning kidney grafts. Of the current patients on hemodialysis, 42.5% were diabetic. The

prevalence of renal replacement therapy (RRT) has increased from 361 per million population (PMP) in 1995 to 874 PMP in 2008. Over the same period, the dialysis patient prevalence has increased from 187 to 463 PMP. The prevalence of ESRD in the USA increased from 1150 PMP in 1995 to 1698 PMP in 2007 and in dialysis from 710 to 1076 PMP.²

A cross sectional study was done in Netherlands and carried out on 15,954 patients with type 2 diabetes or hypertension showed that the prevalence of CKD was 28% in patients with diabetes and 21% in patients with hypertension.⁸

Screening for CKD in primary care is low as Data from 2001 to 2004 showed that in Netherlands only 33% of patients with hypertension or diabetes are screened yearly for serum creatinine, and 10% of patients with diabetes are screened for albuminuria.⁸

Cross-sectional study carried out in India showed that most physicians reported performing routine urinalysis annually on the majority of their patients as recommended by the ADA. Most 86% of physicians reported conducting urinalysis on more than half of their type 1 patients as did 82% for their type 2 patients. Approximately 85% of physicians who screen their patients for albuminuria reported using urine dipsticks most often.⁹

OBJECTIVE:

To assess adherence to nephropathy screening guideline among physicians in chronic disease clinics.

SUBJECTS & METHODS:

Study design, setting and period: The study is a cross-sectional study carried out on Patients with type II diabetes or hypertension or both in chronic disease clinics (CDC) in 4 different PHC centers in Eastern Province from the period of January to July, 2019. The PHC centers are Aljiser District PHC, Alaqrabiyah PHC, Ibn Hayan PHC, Alkhazama PHC.

Sample size: We assumed prevalence 50%, a precision 5%, an alpha level of 5%, the calculated minimum sample size is 246 patient's file.

Inclusion Criteria: Patients' files in chronic disease clinic for male and female, diagnosed with type II diabetes, hypertension or both with or without other comorbidities.

Exclusion Criteria: Type I diabetes mellitus and other chronic diseases.

Sampling technique: Accredited trainees of the family medicine training program from the PHC centers were collecting the data through unified data extraction sheets.

Data collection tools: Data extraction sheet designed for the purpose of this study will be used. The form contained variables such as Age, Sex, Smoking status, Blood pressure (BP), HbA1C, creatinine level, eGFR, proteinuria, Urine albumin creatinine ratio (UACR) and referral.

Study procedures: Then, we collected the total number of type II DM, hypertensive patients or both in chronic disease clinics who follow up regularly from all centers. After that, we selected the consecutive sample from the total.

Data was collected by using data extraction sheet through reviewing medical records which were filled by investigators. Recommended tests data were collected for the past one year (from January to December 2018). The study was carried out during December 2018.

Data management and statistical analysis: The collected data were entered and analyzed using the Statistical Package for the Social Science (SPSS Inc. Chicago, IL, USA) version 23. Descriptive statistics was performed. Percentages were given for qualitative variables and Mean (\pm SD) were given for quantitative variables. The primary study outcome (prevalence of adherence to DN screening according to Saudi Guidelines) were presented as percentage and 95% CI.

Ethical consideration: Privacy of patients' information and confidentiality were carefully

maintained. We received approval from family medicine joint program director which was given to primary health care center managers to conduct our study.

RESULTS:

Table (1): The study included 246 patients, the majority 51.6% was females and 48.4% males. There were 73.2% Saudi and 26.8% non-Saudi. There majority of patients were never smoker 76.4% followed by 18.7% smokers and only 4.9% were ex-smokers. 40.2% of patients had type 2 diabetes mellitus, 24.4% had hypertension and 35.4% had both. Blood pressure was controlled in 69.9 % of patients. HbA1c was ≥ 7 in 41.9% of patients, < 7 in 31.7% and not done in 25.2% of them. More than half of patients (56.9%) had serum creatinine (1) in past 1 years, 67.5% had 0 ACR number and 93.5% of them had 0 proteinuria in past 1 year.

Table (2): Regarding to guideline following, there were 26% of cases follow guideline in screening.

Table (3): 16.3% of patients had moderate (60-89) eGFR, 11.4% had high (≥ 90) eGFR and 10.6% had low (< 60) eGFR. In males 25.6% had normal creatinine levels followed by high in 69% of them however, in females the majority (21.5%) had high level in creatinine followed by normal in 13% of them.

Table (4): As regards relation between guideline following and sociographic characters, there were no significant correlations with age and gender. Also, there was no relation found with diagnosis of patients and nationality ($P > 0.05$).

Table (1): Patients' clinical data (N=246)

VARIABLE	NO.	%
Primary Health Care Center (PHC)		
• Aljiser District PHC	62	25.2
• Alagrabiyah PHC	66	26.8
• Ibn Hayan PHC	57	23.2
• Alkhozama PHC	61	24.8
Gender		
• Male	119	48.4
• Female	127	51.6
Age Groups (years)		
• ≥ 70	29	11.8
• 51-69	135	54.9
• ≤ 50	82	33.3
Nationality		
• Saudi	180	73.2
• Non-Saudi	66	26.8
Smoking		
• Current smoker	46	18.7
• Never smoker	188	76.4
• Ex-smoker	12	4.9
Diagnosis		
• Type II DM	99	40.2
• Hypertension	60	24.4
• Both	87	35.4
BP Control (Based on the last 3 readings)		
• Controlled	172	69.9
• Uncontrolled	33	13.4
• N/A	41	16.7
HbA1C (Latest value in the past 1 year)		
• < 7	78	31.7
• ≥ 7	103	41.9
• Not done	62	25.2
• N/A	3	1.2
Number of serum creatinine in past 1 year		
• None	69	28.0
• 1	140	56.9
• 2	30	12.2
• 3	7	2.8
Number of ACR in past 1 year		
• None	166	67.5
• 1	61	24.8
• 2	15	6.1
• 3	4	1.6
Number of proteinuria in past 1 year		
• None	230	93.5
• 1	13	5.3
• 2	3	1.2

Table (2): Guideline following; frequency and 95% CI.

GUIDELINES FOLLOWED	NO.	%	95% CONFIDENCE INTERVAL (CI)
Followed	64	26.0	(20%-32%)
Not Followed	182	74.0	

Table (3): Distribution of the results of eGFR and Serum Creatinine levels in males and females.

VARIABLES	NO.	%
eGFR		
• High (≥ 90)	28	11.4
• Moderate (60-89)	40	16.3
• Low (< 60)	26	10.6
• Total	94	38.2
• N/A	152	61.8
Mean (+SD)	77.5(27.0)	
Creatinine Levels Males (N=89)		
• High	17	6.9
• Normal	63	25.6
• Low	9	3.7
• Missing	28	5.3
Mean (+SD)	89.64(22.16)	
Creatinine levels (Females) (N=127)		
• High	53	21.5
• Normal	32	13.0
• Low	2	.8
• N/A	40	64.6
Mean (+SD)	94.9(29.9)	

	GUIDELINES FOLLOWING		TOTAL (N=246)	P VALUE
	Followed (n=64)	Not Followed (n=182)		
Age Group (years)				
• ≥ 70	10 (34.5%)	19 (65.5%)	29 (100.0%)	0.538
• 51-69	34 (25.2%)	101 (74.8%)	135 (100.0%)	
• ≤ 50	20 (24.4%)	62 (75.6%)	82 (100.0%)	
Gender				
• Male	31 (26.1%)	88 (73.9%)	119 (100.0%)	0.553
• Female	33 (26.0%)	94 (74.0%)	127 (100.0%)	
Diagnosis				
• Type II DM	29 (29.3%)	70 (70.7%)	99 (100.0%)	0.607
• Hypertension	15 (25.0%)	45 (75.0%)	60 (100.0%)	
• Both	20 (23.0%)	67 (77.0%)	87 (100.0%)	
Nationality				
• Saudi	47 (26.1%)	133 (73.9%)	180 (100.0%)	0.548
• Non-Saudi	17 (25.8%)	49 (74.2%)	66 (100.0%)	

DISCUSSION:

Chronic kidney disease (CKD) is a major global health problem with an increasing prevalence, due to aging of the population and rising incidence of hypertension and diabetes [10]. CKD is associated with a high risk of cardiovascular morbidity, mortality and deterioration to end-stage renal disease (ESRD) [11]. CKD represents a significant public health problem, with nearly 20 million people in the United States having kidney damage or reduced kidney function [12]. More than 400,000 people currently receive some form of renal replacement therapy, and this number is expected to reach 2.2 million by the year 2030 [13]. Chronic kidney disease (CKD), defined as either decreased glomerular filtration rate (GFR) or albuminuria, or both [11]. Also, it is defined by indicators of kidney damage—imaging or proteinuria (commonly using albumin to creatinine ratio, ACR)—and decreased renal function (below thresholds of GFR estimated from serum creatinine concentration) [14, 15].

Diabetes and hypertension are major causes of CKD [16]. Therefore, current international guidelines recommend yearly screening for CKD in patients with diabetes or hypertension [17, 18]. Diabetes is the leading cause of CKD, demonstrated for 33% of the adult cases with CKD [19]. Nevertheless, 20% to 40% of diabetics will develop diabetic nephropathy during the end stage of their disease [20]. The initial presentation of diabetic kidney disease is microalbuminuria followed by increasing severity of proteinuria as the glomerular filtration membrane is damaged [21]. Also, hypertension represents a powerful risk factor for CKD and is almost fixedly found in patients with renal failure. Sodium retention and activation of the renin-angiotensin system have been regarded as the most effective mechanisms implicated in the rising of blood pressure in patients with CKD [22].

Guidelines can be defined as a document that streamlines particular processes according to a regular routine. In the medical context it refers to a document which seeks to guide decisions and criteria regarding diagnosis, management/treatment in specific areas of healthcare [23]. Guidelines identify, summarize and evaluate evidence of the highest quality and the most up-to-date data about prevention, diagnosis, prognosis, therapy including dosages of medications, risk/benefit and cost-effectiveness [24]. There are a variety of barriers to guideline adherence, of which the doctor, patient and practice factors play an important role. According to adherence to guidelines in screening of nephropathy, our study reported that there

were 26% of cases followed guidelines in screening. Generally, compliance with screening for CKD by primary care providers is low [25]. Another study found that overall, adherence by GPs to the guideline recommendations regarding a consultation or referral was low [26]. Also, another study reported only 8.3% of the patient's recommendations from CKD guidelines with respect to consultation and referral to specialist care were followed [27]. However, another study conducted among patients with type II diabetes reported; compliance rate for microalbuminuria screening was 56.3% which was higher than the quoted national average of 14–49% [28].

Currently, screening for chronic kidney disease is accepted practice only in patients with hypertension or diabetes, [29] but more widespread screening is increasingly proposed [30]. The United Kingdom chronic kidney disease guidelines also recommend at least annual screening of all adults at risk of obstructive kidney disease and those with prevalent cardiovascular diseases, [31] while the US kidney disease outcomes quality initiative (US KDOQI) guidelines use age >60 for additional inclusion [14]. Both guidelines highlight the risk associated with multisystem diseases and nephrotoxic drugs. Although evidence to recommend routine screening is insufficient, the tests often suggested for screening CKD that are feasible in primary care include creatinine-derived estimates of glomerular filtration rate (GFR), as well as urine testing for albumin (micro- or microalbuminuria) [32]. Current Kidney Disease: Improving Global Outcomes (KDIGO) guidelines encourage clinicians to monitor both GFR and albumin annually—more frequently in selected patients—to consider the risk of disease progression and therapeutic management [33].

Regarding to screening tests, our study found that 16.3% of patients had moderate (60-89) eGFR, 11.4% had high (≥ 90) eGFR and 10.6% had low (<60) eGFR. In males 25.6% had normal creatinine levels followed by high in 6'9% of them however, in females the majority (21.5%) had high level in creatinine followed by normal in 13% of them.

As regards relation between guideline following and sociographic characters, our study found that there were no significant correlations with age and gender. Also, there was no relation found with diagnosis of patients and nationality ($P > 0.05$).

CONCLUSION:

The study concluded that the majority of cases do not follow nephropathy screening guideline. Therefore,

we recommend decision makers to conduct further planning on increase awareness to physicians and patient about importance of nephropathy screening program , and making physicians perform all the screening measures according to the provided guidelines in order to increase the adherence level and the outcomes of the screening program.

REFERENCES:

1. Al-Sayers AA, Shaheen FA. End stage chronic kidney disease in Saudi Arabia. A rapidly changing scene. Saudi medical journal. 2011;32(4):339-46.
2. Douglas C, Almutary HH, Bonner A. Chronic kidney disease in Saudi Arabia: a nursing perspective. Middle East Journal of Nursing. 2013 Dec;7(6):17-25.
3. James PA, Oparil S, Carter BL, Cushman WC, Dennison-Himmelfarb C, Handler J, Lackland DT, LeFevre ML, MacKenzie TD, Oggedegbe O, Smith SC. 2014 evidence-based guideline for the management of high blood pressure in adults: report from the panel members appointed to the Eighth Joint National Committee (JNC 8). Jama. 2014 Feb 5;311(5):507-20.
4. Nice.org.uk. (2014). Chronic kidney disease in adults: assessment and management | Guidance and guidelines | NICE. [online] Available at: <https://www.nice.org.uk/guidance/cg182/chapter/1-Recommendations#classification-of-chronic-kidney-disease-2>
5. American Diabetes Association. 10. Microvascular complications and foot care. Diabetes care. 2017 Jan 1;40(Supplement 1):S88-98.
6. Elmourad Mourad, Aljasir Salah, Alhamid Mohammed, Altanner Mohammed, Alqaysy Samir, AlSlail Faitma. Saudi National Reference Of Clinical Guidelines For Care Of Diabetic Patients –quick guide./ ministry of health – Riyadh , 2014:13-14.
7. Abdulrhman Aldukhayel. Prevalence of diabetic nephropathy among Type 2 diabetic patients in some of the Arab countries. Int J Health Sci (Qassim). 2017 Jan-Mar; 11(1): 1–4.
8. van der Meer V, Wielders HP, Grootendorst DC, de Kanter JS, Sijpkens YW, Assendelft WJ, Gussekloo J, Dekker FW, Groeneveld Y. Chronic kidney disease in patients with diabetes mellitus type 2 or hypertension in general practice. Br J Gen Pract. 2010 Dec 1;60(581):884-90.
9. Kraft SK, Lazaridis EN, Qiu C, Clark CM, Marrero DG. Screening and treatment of diabetic nephropathy by primary care physicians. Journal of general internal medicine. 1999 Feb 1;14(2):88-97.
10. Coresh J Selvin E Stevens LA et al. Prevalence of chronic kidney disease in the United States. JAMA 2007; 298: 2038–47.
11. Go AS Chertow GM Fan D et al. Chronic kidney disease and the risks of death, cardiovascular events, and hospitalization. N Engl J Med 2004; 351: 1296–305.
12. Coresh J, Astor BC, Greene T, Eknoyan G, Levey AS: Prevalence of chronic kidney disease and decreased kidney function in the adult US population: Third National Health and Nutrition Examination Survey. Am J Kidney Dis 41 :1–12,2003.
13. US Renal Data System: USRDS 2005 Annual Data Report: Atlas of End-Stage Renal Disease in the United States, Bethesda, National Institutes of Health, National Institute of Diabetes and Digestive and Kidney Diseases,2005
14. K/DOQI clinical practice guidelines for chronic kidney disease: evaluation, classification, and stratification. Kidney disease outcome quality initiative. Am J Kidney Dis 2002;39:S1-246.
15. NICE NICE. CG73 Chronic kidney disease: full guideline: 2008; 2008. [6th June 2012]. The published full clinical guideline on Chronic kidney disease including recommendations and methods used.].
16. National Kidney Foundation (2002) K/DOQI clinical practice guidelines for chronic kidney disease: evaluation, classification, and stratification. Am J Kidney Dis 39(2 Suppl 1):S1–S266.
17. American Diabetes Association(2009) Standards of medical care in diabetes. Diabetes Care 32(Suppl 1):S13–S61.
18. Graham I, Atar D, Borch-Johnsen K, et al. (2007) European guidelines on cardiovascular disease prevention in clinical practice: executive summary: Fourth Joint Task Force of the European Society of Cardiology and other societies on cardiovascular disease prevention in clinical practice (constituted by representatives of nine societies and by invited experts). Eur J Cardiovasc Prev Rehabil 14(Suppl 2):E1–40.
19. National Kidney Foundation. K/DOQI clinical practice guidelines for chronic kidney disease: evaluation, classification, and stratification. Am J Kidney Dis 2002; 39(2 Suppl 1): S1–266.
20. Levin A, Singer J, Thompson CR, Ross H, Lewis M. Prevalent LVH in the predialysis population: identifying opportunities for intervention. Am J Kidney Dis. 1996; 27: 347–354.
21. Ernesto L. Schiffrin, Mark L. Lipman, Johannes F.E. Mann. Cardiovascular Involvement in

- General Medical Conditions; Chronic Kidney Disease: Effects on the Cardiovascular System. *Circulation*. 2007; 116: 85-97.
22. Guyton AC, Coleman TG, Wilcox CS. Quantitative analysis of the pathophysiology of hypertension. *J Am Soc Nephrol*. 1999; 10: 2248–2249.
23. Harrison MB, Legare F, Graham LD, Fervers B. Adapting clinical practice guidelines to local context and assessing barriers to their use. *CMAJ*. 2010;182:E78–E84.
24. Cluzeau FA, Burgers JS, Brouwers M. The AGREE Collaboration. Development and validation of an international appraisal instrument for assessing the quality of clinical practice guidelines: The AGREE project. *Qual Saf Health Care*. 2003;12:18–23.
25. Nielen MMJ, Schellevis FG, Verheij RA. [Prevention of chronic kidney disease in primary care] in Dutch. Utrecht: NIVEL; 2006.
26. Carola van Dipten, Saskia van Berkel, Vincent A van Gelder, Jack FM Wetzels, Reinier P Akkermans, Wim JC de Grauw, Marion CJ Biermans, Nynke D Scherpbier-de Haan, Willem JJ Assendelft, Adherence to chronic kidney disease guidelines in primary care patients is associated with comorbidity, *Family Practice*, Volume 34, Issue 4, August 2017, Pages 459–466, <https://doi.org/10.1093/fampra/cmz002>
27. van Gelder VA Scherpbier ND van Berkel Set al. Web-based consultation between general practitioners and nephrologists, a cluster randomized controlled trial *Fam Pract* (in press).
28. Anabtawi A, Mathew LM. Improving compliance with screening of diabetic patients for microalbuminuria in primary care practice. *ISRN Endocrinol*. 2013;2013:893913. Published 2013 Oct 9. doi:10.1155/2013/893913.
29. American Diabetes Association. Standards of medical care in diabetes—2006. *Diabetes Care* 2006;29:S4-42.
30. de Jong PE, Brenner BM. From secondary to primary prevention of progressive renal disease: the case for screening for albuminuria. *Kidney Int* 2004;66:2109-18.
31. Chronic kidney disease in adults: UK guidelines for identification, management and referral of adults. www.renal.org/CKDguide (assessed Dec 2005)
32. Moyer, Virginia A. "Screening for chronic kidney disease: US Preventive Services Task Force recommendation statement." *Annals of internal medicine* 157.8 (2012): 567-570.
33. KDIGO 2012 Clinical Practice Guideline for the Evaluation and Management of Chronic Kidney Disease. *Kidney Intl*. 2013 Jan;3(1):1–150.